

Estimation of Energy Savings for Cool Roof in Residential Building in India

Satheesh Kumar.S

Department of Mechanical Engineering,
Nehru Institute of Technology,
Coimbatore,
Tamilnadu, India.
satheeshmkg@gmail.com

Sekar.M,

Department of Mechanical Engineering,
Government College of Technology,
Coimbatore,
Tamilnadu, India
sekargctc@gmail.com

Ramesh.C,

Department of Mechanical Engineering,
Kalaignar Karunanidhi Institute of Technology,
Coimbatore,
Tamilnadu, India
rameshgct12@gmail.com

Abstract

Cool roof surfaces are highly reflective and are least heated by Sunlight. By reflecting most of the incident sun rays which may otherwise heat the living space, cool roofs can be helpful in maintaining the buildings and environment cooler. Application of cool roofs lessens the consumption of electricity for cooling needs. Minimizing the usage of Air conditioners will keep the Global warming in control by reducing the liberation of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. While several options available for converting the standard roof into cool roof, cool paints seems to be the promising alternate. This paper compares the different softwares available for simulating the energy savings by cool roof and presents the energy savings of a cool roof over normal roof with the real time data from the southern part of India.

Keywords: Cool Roof Calculator, Thermal Comfort, Energy Savings, Reflective Paint, Urban Heat Island mitigation

Nomenclature

NatHERS	Nationwide House Energy Rating Scheme
RSC	Roof Savings Calculator
DOE	Department of Energy
TRHG	Through Roof Heat Gain
PCM	Phase Changing Material
TRNSYS	Transient System Simulation tool
PMV	Predicted Mean Vote
SHGC	Solar Heat Gain Coefficient
ESPC	Energy Savings Performance Contract
IPMVP	International Performance and Measurement Protocol
ICE	Indoor Climate and Energy
EDSL	Environmental Design Solutions Limited
HVAC	Heat, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
ISO	International Organisation for Standardization
ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigerating, and Air-Conditioning Engineers
PPD	Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied
TNEB	Tamil Nadu Electricity Board
LCC	Life Cycle Cost
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
SRI	Solar Reflective Index
Rs	Rupees (Indian Currency)
INR	Indian Rupees

1. INTRODUCTION

Cool roofs can help many building owners save money while protecting the environment. A cool roof can be desirable to a building owner for several reasons. Cool roofs can reduce energy bills by decreasing air conditioning needs, improve indoor thermal comfort for spaces that are not air conditioned and decrease roof operating temperature, which may extend roof service life. Cool roofs can reduce local air temperatures, which improves air quality and slows smog formation; reduce peak electric power demand, which can help prevent power outages; reduce power plant emissions, including carbon dioxide, sulphur dioxide, nitrous oxides, and mercury, by reducing cooling energy use in buildings; and reduce heat trapped in the atmosphere by reflecting more sunlight back into space, which can slow climate change¹. The Australian NatHERS establishes the protocols and standardises software that can be utilised by the design-construction industry for the purposes of determining design compliance with the energy efficiency regulations of the National Construction Code. All software accredited under this national scheme calculates the heat flows into and out of the building envelope on an hourly basis to determine the space heating and cooling loads for each zone of the house². Haidong Wang et al. provides an overview of advancements in simulation and computational techniques covering a variety of aspects of buildings including ventilation performance prediction, whole building energy and thermal load simulation, lighting and day lighting modeling, building information modeling, indoor acoustic simulation, and life cycle analysis of buildings³.

2. SIMULATION SOFTWARES

A web-based Roof Savings Calculator (RSC) has been deployed for the United States Department of Energy as an industry-consensus tool to help building owners, manufacturers, distributors, contractors and researchers easily run complex roof and attic simulations. Roof Savings Calculator provides an approach-able portal for both industry experts and residential homeowners to leverage the best available whole-building energy simulation packages and determine energy and cost savings for modern roof technologies and related retrofits⁴. There exists two internet based calculators for understanding the benefits of cool roofs: DOE's cool roof calculator, the closely-related DOE Steep Slope Calculator and the roof savings calculator. All tools are developed for the United States (US) and either use DOE 2.1 platform for simulations or lookup tables based on data from experimental facilities in the US⁵.

Hashem Akbari et al. in California modelled the building with the DOE-2.1E program using the collected data on air-conditioning electricity use, indoor and outdoor temperatures and humidities, roof and ceiling surface temperatures, inside and outside wall temperatures, insolation, and wind speed and direction and they identified that applying a high-albedo coating to one house results in seasonal savings of 2.2 kWh/d (80% of base case use), and peak demand reductions of 0.6 kW⁶. Akbari et al. proposed a monetary savings for 11 US Metropolitan cities using DOE-2 building energy simulation program and estimated that the annual peak electricity power can be reduced to 7 GW⁷. The energy consumption of commercial buildings in Montreal (Canada) with absorptive and reflective skin materials were investigated using DOE-2building energy model. Calculated energy consumption and energy expenditure showed that, in general, increasing the reflectivity of building skin saves energy and money. The surface modification is more beneficial for old vintage buildings⁸.

2.1 EnergyPlus

Kibria K. Roman et al. compares the cool Roof with Phase change materials for mitigating heat island effect in US using the EnergyPlus simulation software. The results demonstrate that the maximum TRHG flux was 54% lower for the PCM roof than the cool roof at a wide range of albedo. Similarly, the maximum sensible heat flux for the PCM roof type was 40% lower than the cool roof technology for varying albedo⁹. Soolyeon Cho analyzes the thermal energy demand and consumption between the two different building types such as residential house and commercial office building by EnergyPlus V6.0. This paper discusses the potential issues and challenges for implementing the load sharing systems as well as the possible solutions for these issues in South Korea¹⁰. Aviruch Bhatia et al. created a model of the building, which uses Energy plus as the simulation engine. He analyse the energy savings through Cool Roof for the different geographical regions including Mumbai (warm and humid climate), followed by Ahmedabad (hot and dry climate), Bangalore (temperate climate), and Delhi (composite climate) in India¹¹.

EnergyPlus simulations of standard compliant Chinese office and residential building prototypes in seven Chinese cities (Harbin, Changchun, Beijing, Chongqing, Shanghai, Wuhan and Guangzhou) showed that substituting an aged white roof (albedo 0.6) for an aged gray roof (albedo 0.2) yields positive annual load, energy, energy cost, CO₂, NO_x, and SO₂ savings in all hot-summer cities (Chongqing, Shanghai, Wuhan and Guangzhou). Measurements in an office building in Chongqing in August 2012 found that a white coating lowered roof surface temperature by about 20°C, and reduced daily air conditioning energy use by about 9%¹².

Boyano et al. identified through EnergyPlus that by reducing the equivalent operating time by installing partial or total lighting control can result in total energy savings of up to 18% (for partial lighting control) or 36% (for total lighting control). The energy savings potential due to the orientation of the building results in an average energy savings between 3 and 6%¹³. Griffith and Crawley proposed a methodology which uses EnergyPlus for evaluating the energy performance for the US commercial building sector to estimate the technical potential of zero-energy buildings¹⁴.

An optimization in the thickness of its thermal insulation layer is investigated by using EnergyPlus software for a small residential house in Serbia and the results show the optimal thickness of thermal insulation that yields the minimum primary energy consumption¹⁵. Rathish Sathyabama Arumugam et al. with the EnergyPlus V7.1 software, analyze a single storey office building in India. Research results show that for a roof with albedo of 0.6 and radiant barrier emittance of 0.2, the optimized roof R-value is 0.49m² K/W in hot, dry and composite climates, 0.31m² K/W in warm and humid and temperate climates, and 1.02m² K/W for cold climates¹⁶. Jahangir Alam et al. proposed a simple methodology to estimate source and site energy where maximum energy requirement are 1485.14 MJ/m² and 447.6 MJ/m² respectively. The evaluation of building energy consumption was carried out by EnergyPlus. The methodology has been applied to hypothetical buildings in Jessore, Bangladesh¹⁷. The results of the study by Michele De Carli et al. using EnergyPlus shows that using a cool roofing material in the Mediterranean area for industrial premises leads to significant sensible cooling energy savings up to 42% and 40-50% and the possibilities of reduction in roof surface temperature using Cool Roof materials¹⁸.

2.2 TRNSYS

Calise et al. modelled and implemented a single-lumped capacitance building in the computer code using TRNSYS to simulate the systems performance for dynamic heating/cooling loads¹⁹. Ankur Khandelwal et al. carried out the heat load calculations and building simulation using TRNSYS software. The annual energy consumptions, the indoor temperature, the relative humidity and the thermal comfort index PMV are compared for three different air-conditioning systems. The coupling of direct and regenerative evaporative cooling technologies with water chiller system has shown, respectively, 12.09% and 15.69% savings in annual energy consumption of the building, while maintaining PMV between -1 and +1 for most of the hours in the year²⁰. In order to estimate the effect of the use of cool and cool coloured materials on the residential energy load, simulations were performed for 27 cities around the world representing different climatic conditions, including Mediterranean, humid continental, subtropical arid, desert conditions, etc. TRNSYS thermal simulation software was used for the simulations. The results show that increasing the roof solar reflectance reduces cooling loads by 18–93% and peak cooling demand in air-conditioned buildings by 11–27%²¹. TRNSYS was used to model the building and simulate the cooling load characteristics in Malaysia. Cooling load characteristics of the academic building using the current and proposed technique were compared and the results showed that annual energy saving potential as much as 305,150 kW h can be achieved²².

2.3 WINDOW

Pablo J. Rosado et al. estimated the Monthly window heat fluxes (energy/area) with the Sustainable by design window heat gain tool using window SHGC and orientations reported in

building plans. The SHGC of each window and its covering (curtain or blind) was estimated using WINDOW software assuming surface-normal solar incidence. Each monthly heat gain (energy per area) was then multiplied by window area and divided by its time interval (seconds in a month) to calculate its contribution to the rate of window heat gain, window Q (power/area)²³.

2.4 eQUEST

Ming-Tsun Ke et al. examines the ESPC of an office building in Taiwan by applying IPMVP in combination with the energy analysis model established for the building by eQUEST simulation software to calibrate energy consumption simulation results using actual electricity billing data²⁴.

2.5 Indoor Climate and Energy software

IDA ICE is a building performance simulations tool to model buildings with wide variety of heating and cooling systems. It is an hourly dynamic simulation program which is an equation based model, using either the Modelica language or the Neutral Model Format²⁶. Kimmo Hilliaho et al. investigated the effect of adding the glazing on the building in Sweden. Measurements were taken on site and were used as the input for computational studies performed with the help of IDA-ICE software. The study shows that the heating energy demand was reduced after the glazing installation by between 5.6% and 25.3%. In addition, the mean annual temperature difference between the cavity space and the outside air was from 5.2°C to 11.4°C higher²⁵. To evaluate the annual energy use of the test cabins depending on the surface radiation properties under a controlled set of conditions, the simulation program IDA-ICE was used by Ali Joudi et al²⁶.

2.6 EDSL TAS

Xiaoxin Wang et al. used the Dynamic thermal simulation software EDSL TAS version 9.0.9 to build a geometrically precise model of a typical retail shed for analyzing the effect of Solar reflective coating in six locations around the world. The modelling and computational results prove that the use of solar reflective coatings is effective in reducing cooling load and overall electricity consumption for most locations, in particular in hot climates with predominant cooling requirements²⁷.

3. EQUIPMENT AND LIGHTING LOADS

Lighting, HVAC equipment, water heaters, and Appliances consume energy in the form of either electricity or fuel. All of these data are important to understand and optimize for high performance building design, and are important inputs for whole building energy analysis simulation²⁸.

3.1 Equipment Power Density

Equipment, like HVAC systems and water heaters, is the other main internal load. This is typically separated from plug loads and is given in terms of an Equipment Power Density, which is measured in Watts per square foot or square meter²⁸.

3.2 Lighting Power Density

The electrical power consumed by fixed lighting installations per unit floor area of an illuminated space is termed as Lighting Power Density²⁹.

3.3 Predicted Mean Vote

PMV refers to a thermal scale that runs from Cold (-3) to Hot (+3), originally developed by Fanger and later adopted as an ISO standard. The original data was collected by subjecting a large number of people (reputedly many thousands of Israeli soldiers) to different conditions within a climate chamber and having them select a position on the scale the best described their comfort sensation. A mathematical model of the relationship between all the environmental and physiological factors considered was then derived from the data. The result relates the size thermal comfort factors to each other through heat balance principles and produces the following sensation scale. The recommended acceptable PMV range for thermal comfort from ASHRAE 55 is between -0.5 and +0.5 for an interior space³⁰.

3.4 Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied

PPD predicts the percentage of occupants that will be dissatisfied with the thermal conditions. It is a function of PMV, given that as PMV moves further from 0, or neutral, PPD increases. The maximum number of people dissatisfied with their comfort conditions is 100% and, as you can never please all of the people all of the time, the recommended acceptable PPD range for thermal comfort from ASHRAE 55 is less than 10% persons dissatisfied for an interior space³⁰.

4. METHODOLOGY

Nelson Fumo et al. presents a simple methodology to estimate hourly electrical and fuel energy consumption of a building by applying a series of predetermined coefficients to the monthly energy consumption data from electrical and fuel utility bills. The advantage of having predetermined coefficients is that it relieves the user from the burden of performing a detailed dynamic simulation of the building³¹. Based on the electrical consumption data provided by TNEB³² for a residential building in Trichy, Southern part of Tamilnadu, an analysis was carried out for estimating the energy savings of Cool Roof over Normal Roof by using the Cool Roof Calculator V3³³.

Table 1 represent the slab rate in Tamil Nadu. Energy meter reading and current consumption charges are shown in the Table 2.

Readings are taken once in two months in Tamil Nadu. The actual consumption of electricity from Nov 2014 to September 2016 was shown in the Figure 1. The Power consumption charges for the residential building selected for study was revealed in the Figure 2.

Table 1. Slab rate

From Unit	To Unit	Rate (Rs.)	Maximum Unit
1	100	1	100
1	200	1.5	200
1	200	2	500
201	500	3	500
1	200	3.5	9999999
201	500	4.6	9999999
501	Above	6.6	9999999

Table2. Energy meter Reading and current consumption charges

Reading taken Date	Reading	Used Unit	CC Charges (Rs.)	Other Charges (Rs.)	Bill Amount (Rs.)	Adv. Amount (Rs.)	Adj. Amount (Rs.)	Total Bill Amount (Rs.)	Due Date	Bill Paid	Receipt No	Payment Date
06/09/18	7880	230	290	30	320	0	0	320	26/09/18	18320	PGNIDB1491555	12/09/18
05/07/18	7650	250	404	30	434	0	0	434	25/07/18	18434	PGNIDB1390231	14/07/18
09/05/18	7400	370	910	30	940	0	0	940	30/05/18	18940	PGNIDB1280527	16/05/18
07/03/18	7030	200	300	20	320	0	0	320	28/03/18	18320	PGNIDB1169130	14/03/18
06/01/18	6830	150	225	20	245	0	0	245	25/01/18	18245	PGNKVB5861944	17/01/18
05/11/17	6680	170	255	20	275	0	0	275	24/11/17	17275	PGNIDB954567	06/11/17
07/09/17	6510	140	210	20	230	0	0	230	26/09/17	17230	PGNIDB857735	07/09/17
07/07/17	6370	100	100	20	120	0	0	120	27/07/17	17120	PGNIDB772608	07/07/17
07/05/17	6270	200	300	20	320	0	0	320	26/05/17	17320	PGNIDB692844	11/05/17
10/03/17	6070	180	270	20	290	0	0	290	30/03/17	17290	PGNSBI1823998	12/03/17
08/01/17	5890	110	165	20	185	0	0	185	27/01/17	17185	TIV296AR2S632	14/01/17
07/11/16	5780	130	195	20	215	0	0	215	26/11/16	16215	TIV296AR2S863	15/11/16

Figure 1. Actual Consumed Units

Figure 2. Electricity usage charges

One of the major challenges in applying Cool Roof is selecting the most appropriate material for the building location and roof type. There is wide variety of cool roof materials with differences in their emissivity, reflectivity, life and initial cost. Performance of each of the materials varies over a wide range with change in climatic conditions, roof type, HVAC system type, etc. Availability of a wide range of varieties and their varying performance with various prevailing conditions, are the two major reasons because of which estimation of energy savings from Cool Roofs is difficult. Correct choice of the Cool Roof material should therefore be made by considering various building features, keeping into consideration the Life Cycle Cost (LCC).

4.2 Tool Description

Cool roof Calculator uses the mentioned parameters as input and calculates the resultant energy savings and the LCC for various types of Cool Roofing materials and technologies. The Calculator helps in comparing two identical building models that differ by the roof external finish. Either the simple or detail calculator can be used to input the parameters of the building, based on which the energy savings and payback, or the comfort shall be calculated. In the simple form, details such as roof type, roof finish, roof area and HVAC system type are the inputs. In the detail form, the building envelope data includes details such as: the window to wall ratio on each of the four major orientations of the exterior walls, roof insulation detail, the normal roof solar reflectivity and the cool roof solar reflectivity. Internal loads such as the equipment and the lighting power density are also the inputs to be provided. Various loads on the building are depicted in the Table 3.

Table 3. Internal load on the Residential building

Appliances	Watts	No. of Appliances	Average usage hrs/day	Units/month
Tube Light	40	5	3	18
CFL	20	6	5	18
Fan	100	2	16	96
Exhaust Fan	100	1	3	9
AC	1000	1	1	30

The tool works on EnergyPlus v7.1 to run the hourly simulations and calculate the resulted annual savings. Broadly the inputs can be put under the heads of building envelope, internal loads, HVAC, building geometry, and the location. Table 4 shows the necessary inputs required for simulation.

Table 4. Building input Parameters

Required Inputs	Input Data
Location	Trichy
Building	Residential
Roof Area	130 m ²
Roof Layer	150 mm thick RCC slab

By default a square block with perimeter and core zoning is considered for the simulation. Location of the building is another major input which is to be selected. The city in which the building is located can be selected from the list. The solar reflectivity is measured according to ASTM E903. Traditional roofing materials have a Solar Reflective Index (SRI) of 5% (brown shingles) and an emissivity of 0.9³². Table 5 shows the external finish data for the Roof selected for study.

Table 5. Roof External Finish Inputs

Required Inputs	Normal Roof	Cool Roof
Reflectivity	0.3	0.3
Emissivity	0.9	0.9
Cost/m ²	1600	1850
Roof Life	5	5

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Lighting power density and the Equipment power density for Normal Roof with the usage of Air Conditioners are found to be 0.384 and 1.44 W/m² respectively. There was a little decrease in the Equipment power density when it was measured without Air conditioners and the values are listed in Table 6.

Table 6. Energy consumption Calculations for Normal Roof

Savings	With AC (W/m ²)	Without AC (W/m ²)
Lighting power density	0.384	0.384
Equipment power density	1.44	1.121

Overall savings in Electricity consumption with AC was estimated to be 7,273.02 kWh/year corresponds to an equivalent savings in the cost of Rs.33,455.89/year. Table 7 shows the cost and Energy savings on Cool Roof with AC. Internal Cooling loads in Normal roof was higher in comparison with the Cool roof as shown in the Figure 3 and the Indoor Air Temperatures are higher for Normal Roof as revealed in Figure 4.

Table 7. Cost and Energy Savings on cool roof with AC

Savings	Total savings (kWh/year)	Savings per unit area (kWh/m ² per annum)	Saving in cost (INR/year)
Savings in cooling	6,799.11	52.30	Rs. 31,275.91
Overall savings	7,273.02	55.95	Rs. 33,455.89

Figure 3. Monthly Cooling Electricity Consumption

Figure 4. Monthly Indoor Air Temperatures

A steep reduction in the usage of cooling loads in the building model with Cool Roof can be seen from the Table 8. A 36.50% of savings was expected from Cool Roofs over the Normal Roof.

Table 8. Percentage savings in electrical appliances

End Use Category	Electricity [kWh]		Saving (%)
	Normal roof	Cool roof	
Cooling	18628.38	11829.27	36.50
Interior Lighting	37.94	37.94	0.00
Interior Equipment	318.19	318.19	0.00
Fans	1285.93	812.03	36.85
Total	20270.45	12997.43	35.88

Fanger PMV and PPD for Normal and Cool Roofs are presented in Table 9 and 10 respectively.

Table 9. Fanger PMV and PPD for Normal Roof

	Occupied hours [Hours]	Air temperature for occupied hours [C]	Relative Humidity for occupied hours [%]	Fanger PMV for occupied hours	Fanger PPD for occupied hours
January	528.00	29.30	98.71	2.15	80.97
February	480.00	32.30	98.24	3.02	98.68
March	552.00	35.12	98.29	3.87	99.97
April	480.00	37.19	97.90	4.51	99.99
May	552.00	37.83	97.91	5.13	100.00
June	528.00	36.83	98.28	4.72	99.99
July	504.00	36.10	97.74	4.41	99.99
August	552.00	35.72	98.44	4.26	99.99
September	504.00	35.69	98.50	4.25	99.99
October	528.00	34.12	98.61	3.57	99.81
November	528.00	31.09	99.28	2.67	96.14
December	504.00	30.18	99.09	2.41	91.30
Annual Sum or Average	6240.00	34.31	98.42	3.75	97.24
Minimum of Months	480.00	29.30	97.74	2.15	80.97
Maximum of Months	552.00	37.83	99.28	5.13	100.00

Table 10. Fanger PMV and PPD for Cool Roof

Months	Occupied hours [Hours]	Air temperature for occupied hours [C]	Relative Humidity for occupied hours [%]	FangerPMV for occupied hours	FangerPPD for occupied hours
January	528.00	25.82	99.26	1.18	35.21
February	480.00	28.01	98.84	1.78	66.10
March	552.00	30.28	98.97	2.43	90.86
April	480.00	31.97	98.85	2.93	98.61
May	552.00	32.84	98.96	3.10	99.41
June	528.00	32.18	99.01	2.84	97.91
July	504.00	31.62	98.55	2.62	95.35
August	552.00	31.24	99.00	2.47	92.61
September	504.00	31.14	99.13	2.44	91.54
October	528.00	29.88	99.25	2.32	88.09
November	528.00	27.71	99.66	1.70	62.20
December	504.00	26.92	99.51	1.48	50.29
Annual Sum or Average	6240.00	29.99	99.09	2.28	80.83
Minimum of Months	480.00	25.82	98.55	1.18	35.21
Maximum of Months	552.00	32.84	99.66	3.10	99.41

It can be seen from the Figure 5 that the PMV for the Normal Roof is more than the Cool Roof.

Figure 5. Monthly Fanger Predicted Mean Vote

6. CONCLUSION

In this study, a simple methodology was demonstrated to estimate the Energy and cost savings by using Cool Roof calculator V3 for residential building located in Trichy, South India. This methodology will be highly useful for predicting the energy savings for house owners, builders, Architects, Engineers and the Researchers in India. The location for analysis has been selected on the basis to match the data available in the Simulation software. The current consumption data has been collected from the Tamil Nadu Electricity Board web portal. Data of twelve billing cycles has been used as inputs for better results. The Reflectivity and Emissivity values are used as per ASTM E903. It has been estimated that a potential annual savings of 36% was possible by using the cool roof in the selected location. In 5 years duration the extra cost of material for cool roof was Rs. 250 per square meter and the electricity savings are 55.95 kWh/m²/Year (i.e. Rs. 257.37). Simple payback period for replacing the Normal Roof by Cool roof was 0.97 years. Validation of this study is about to be carried out using the indigenously developed Solar Reflective Coating.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the team members Dr.Vishal Garg, Dr.Jyotirmay Mathur, Kshitij Chandrasen, Akshey Jawa, Surekha Tetali and Shikher Somal for making the energy savings simulation easier and adoptable for India.

References

1. Guidelines for Selecting Cool Roofs. Energy Efficiency and renewable Energy, U.S. Department of Energy, 2010, 1- 23.
2. Wendy Miller, Glenn Crompton and John Bell, Analysis of Cool Roof Coatings for Residential Demand Side Management in Tropical Australia. *Energies*, 2015, 8, pp. 5303- 5318.
3. Haidong Wang and Zhiqiang (John) Zhai, *Advances in Building Simulation and Computational Techniques: A Review between 1987 and 2014*. Energy and Buildings, Elsevier, 2016, pp. 1- 50.
4. Joshua New, William A. Miller, Yu (Joe) Huang and Ronnen Levinson, Comparison of software models for energy savings from cool roofs. *Energy and buildings*, Elsevier, 2015, pp. 1- 6.
5. Vishal Garg, Shikher Somal, Rathish Arumugam and Aviruch Bhatia, Development for cool roof calculator for India. *Energy and Buildings*, Elsevier, 2015, pp. 1- 7.
6. Hashem Akbari, Sarah Bretz, Dan M. Kurn and James Hanford, Peak power and cooling energy savings of high-albedo roofs. *Energy and Buildings*, Elsevier, 1997, 25, pp. 117- 126.
7. Akbari, H., Konopacki, S. and Pomerantz, M., Cooling energy savings potential of reflective roofs for residential and commercial buildings in the United States. *Energy*, Elsevier, 1999, 24, pp. 391- 407.

8. Ali G. Touchaei, Mirata Hosseini and Hashem Akbari, Energy savings potentials of commercial buildings by urban heat island reduction strategies in Montreal (Canada). *Energy and Buildings*, Elsevier, 2016, 110, pp. 41- 48.
9. Kibria K. Roman, Timothy O'Brien, Jedediah B. Alvey and OhJin Woo, Simulating the effects of cool roof and PCM (phase change materials) based roof to mitigate UHI (urban heat island) in prominent US cities. *Energy*, Elsevier, 2016, 96, pp. 103-117.
10. Soolyeon Cho, Kwang Ho Lee, Eun Chul Kang and Euy Joon Lee, Energy simulation modeling and savings analysis of load sharing between house and office. *Renewable Energy*, Elsevier, 2013, 54, pp. 70- 77.
11. Aviruch Bhatia, Jyotirmay Mathur and Vishal Garg, Calibrated simulation for estimating energy savings by the use of cool roof in five Indian climatic zones. *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy*, American Institute of Physics, 2011, 3, pp. 023108(1-14).
12. Yafeng Gao, Jiangmin Xu, Shichao Yang, Xiaomin Tang, Quan Zhou, Jing Ge, Tengfang Xu and Ronnen Levinson, Cool roofs in China: Policy review, building simulations, and proof-of-concept experiments. *Energy policy*, Elsevier, 2014, pp. 1- 25.
13. Boyano, A., Hernandez, P. and Wolf, O., Energy demands and potential savings in European office buildings: Case studies based on EnergyPlus simulations. *Energy and Buildings*, Elsevier, 2013, 65, pp. 19- 28.
14. Griffith, B. and Crawley, D., Methodology for Analyzing the Technical Potential for Energy Performance in the US Commercial Building Sector with Detailed Energy Modeling, *Proceedings of SimBuild Conference*, Cambridge, Massachusetts, 2006.
15. Milorad Bojic, Marko Miletic and Ljubisa Bojic, Optimization of thermal insulation to achieve energy savings in low energy house (refurbishment). *Energy Conversion and Management*, Elsevier, 2014, 84, pp. 681- 690.
16. Rathish Sathyabama Arumugam, Vishal Garg, VinayakaRam, V and Aviruch Bhatia, Optimizing roof insulation for roofs with high albedo coating and radiant barriers in India. *Journal of Building Engineering*, Elsevier, 2015, 2, pp. 52- 58.
17. Jahangir Alam, Md., Mohammad Ariful Islam and Biplob Kumar Biswas, Energy simulation to estimate building energy consumption using EnergyPlus, *Proceedings of International Conference on Mechanical, Industrial and Energy Engineering*, Khulna, Bangladesh, 2014.
18. Michele De Carli, Massimiliano Scarpa, Stefano Schiavon and Roberto Zecchin, Simulated Energy Savings of a Cool Roofs applied to Industrial Premises in the Mediterranean Area, *Proceedings of International Conference ClimaMed*, Genoa, Italy, 2007.

19. Calise, F., Palombo, A. and Vanoli, L., Maximization of primary energy savings of solar heating and cooling systems by transient simulations and computer design of experiments. *Applied Energy*, Elsevier, 2010, 87, pp. 524- 540.
20. Ankur Khandelwal, Prabal Talukdar and Sanjeev Jain, Energy savings in a building using regenerative evaporative cooling. *Energy and Buildings*, Elsevier, 2011, 43, pp. 581- 591.
21. Synnefa, A., Santamouris, M. and Akbari, H., Estimating the effect of using cool coatings on energy loads and thermal comfort in residential buildings in various climatic conditions. *Energy & Buildings*, Elsevier, 2007, 39, pp. 1167–1174.
22. Petrus Tri Bhaskoro, Syed Ihtsham Ul Haq Gilani and Mohd Shiraz Aris, Simulation of energy saving potential of a centralized HVAC system in an academic building using adaptive cooling technique. *Energy Conversion and Management*, Elsevier, 2013, 75, pp. 617- 628.
23. Pablo J. Rosado, David Faulkner, Douglas P. Sullivan and Ronnen Levinson, Measured temperature reductions and energy savings from a cool tile roof on a central California home. *Energy and Buildings*, Elsevier, 2014, pp. 1– 56.
24. Ming-Tsun Ke, Chia-Hung Yeh and Jhong-Ting Jian, Analysis of building energy consumption parameters and energy savings measurement and verification by applying eQUEST software. *Energy and Buildings*, Elsevier, 2013, 61, pp. 100- 107.
25. Kimmo Hilliaho, Birgitta Nordquist, Petter Wallentèn, Akram Abdul Hamid and Jukka Lahdensivu, Energy saving and indoor climate effects of an added glazed facade to a brick wall building: case study. *Journal of Building Engineering*, Elsevier, 2016, pp. 1- 26.
26. Ali Joudi, Harald Svedung, Mathias Cehlin and Mats Rönnelid, Reflective coatings for interior and exterior of buildings and improving thermal performance. *Applied Energy*, Elsevier, 2013, 103, pp. 562- 570.
27. Xiaoxin Wang, Chris Kendrick, Ray Ogden and James Maxted, Dynamic thermal simulation of a retail shed with solar reflective coatings. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, Elsevier, 2008, 28, pp. 1066- 1073.
28. <http://sustainabilityworkshop.autodesk.com/buildings/equipment-and-lighting-loads>
29. Code of Practice for Energy Efficiency of Building Services Installation, Electrical and Mechanical Services Department, Hong Kong, 2012.
30. <http://sustainabilityworkshop.autodesk.com/buildings/human-thermal-comfort>
31. Nelson Fumo, Pedro Mago and Rogelio Luck, Methodology to estimate building energy consumption using EnergyPlus benchmark models. *Energy and Buildings*, Elsevier, 2010, 42, pp. 2331–2337.
32. <http://tneb.tnebnet.org/newlt/menu3.html>

33. <http://coolroof.cbs.iiit.ac.in/index.php>